

A Study on Factors That Motivate English-majored Students at HUPI in Speaking Lesson.

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Abstract

English has become more and more popular in Vietnam (Vietnam Teaching Jobs – ESL Teaching Jobs in Vietnam, n.d.). The young generation has more opportunities to enter international and global integration. English- majored students at HUPI (Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry) were trained by the Department of Foreign Languages to meet social needs. Speaking English fluently is an advantage for students after graduation (LaRock, 2019). Therefore, speaking lesson is significant for English- majored students who want to improve speaking skill. The students practice English speaking day by day through the speaking lessons. The purpose of this study was to investigate factors that motivate English- majored students in Speaking lesson. Furthermore, with the implementation of this study, the teacher can finger out the most effective way to help their students in the speaking lesson and English- majored students are also able to improve speaking skills.

Keywords: Vietnam, speaking lesson, speaking skill, English- majored students, factors.

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduce the problem

English is an important language that is used over the world so that it has become a global language nowadays. The opportunities are sharing equal for everyone who is a part of the global community and using English. To be a global citizen, anyone needs to know English. Especially, English-major students who are learning languages need to speak English fluently. Besides, the students who are good at English skills are beneficial in a competitive work environment after graduation. Unfortunately, English speaking is not a strength of students during and after school. English-major students and non-major students are generally facing difficult problems to express their thought effectively. (Hosni, 2014). As a result, many students cannot meet requirements as employers require. To fix this weakness, English speaking lessons can help students to improve speaking skills. This study was conducted with English- major student in HUPI, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. The study was examined over 40 English-majored students to find out factors that motivate them in the Speaking lesson. The methods examined in this study such as questionnaires and formulating recommendations. The expectation in the study is to help teachers apply effective ways which motivate students in speaking lesson.

1.2. Explore importance of the problem

Many reports and research point out a lot of ways to improve speaking skills because everyone can see how speaking skills important is. Obviously, students have to show good English performance after graduation so that they can work and communicate easily in the workplace. However, a question should be asked such as how can motivate students in speaking lessons? and how many factors affect to student's motivation? Many students have no interest in English speaking lessons even though those lessons are very necessary for them to practice English. Besides, the students need to practice as much as possible in speaking lessons after that they can speak English fluently. A speaking lesson demands to have positive effects on students. This study would find the answer to this issue. Moreover, readers can find some information which would help study English.

2. Literature review

Speaking is very important because people express ideas through communication. A baby speaks before he can read or write. Students need to study English early age because according to Kang (2002), speaking a foreign language is not easy for non-native learners oral communication requires different elements in social interactions. Burns and Joyce (1999) stated that speaking combines three factors: producing, receiving and processing information.

In the same line with this study, some relevant research will be review. Theses researches were pointed out factors affecting student motivation in speaking lessons. There are objective and subjective factors such as teacher, class activities, learning environment, students' speaking skill, methodology, ...

Calderhead and Robson (1991) said that teachers play roles importantly in class because they transfer knowledge to students and they determine methodology in the classroom. Objective facts create an individual's knowledge (Pajares, 1992) so that teacher's emotional charge can influence their role. According to Ben-Peretz, Mendelsona & Kronb (2003), the teacher's roles are determined by efficiency in the work and their acknowledgment. Beijaard (2000) and colleagues found that there are three main roles for the teacher. The teacher is a subject matter expert to solve problems and questions. The teacher can be a pedagogical expert because they have a specific skill for teaching. Also, the teacher is a didactical expert. Combining three roles influence the development of the student and behavior in the classroom. The teacher create positive energy in class and make students exciting during the lesson. Other authors affirmed that a learning environment can promote students during lessons so that teachers should apply teaching methods and learning strategies to support their students (Radovan, 2011). Teachers is clearly understanding their role that is to design, create and manage the student's learning process (Poom-Valickis, Oder, & Lepik, 2012). Furthermore, the student tends to like studying in a subject that was taught by their favorite teacher. The connection between teacher and student can make the lesson successful. The teacher should be a friend who students can talk and share because the understanding mentality of their student would be more beneficial in the teaching process.

Class activities also support successful lessons especially English-speaking lessons. Hayriye (2006) stated that there are a lot of activities that the teacher can create for the student in speaking class such as discussion, role play, simulation, information map, brainstorming, storytelling, interviews, story completion, reporting, playing cards, picture narrating, picture describing, find the difference. Hayriye also pointed out that the goal of class activities is to lead students to pure memorization and provide an English environment for communication. Furthermore, he mentioned that students can develop basic interactive skills through class activities and speaking lessons would be active, meaningful and fun in the learning process. Uberman (1998) considered that using games is a good way to make a class more interesting and enjoyable. In Gardner's opinion (1999), games increase intelligence for children including interpersonal and kinesthetic intelligence. Brinkmann (2003) found that mind maps use visuals to make student's brain speed up memory and recall information. Besides, Buzan & Buzan (2002) wrote about drawing mind maps personally would help learners support long term memory and retrieve information easily. Rossiter (2002) said that storytelling is an effective tool for teaching because stories are rememberable and entertaining. Students tend to remember information that links to fact stories like human experience because that information reminds about the actions of the characters. Therefore, students are easy to remember if they join in class activities.

Everyone can be affected by emotion when they work or study. The student is not an exception. Their mood changes day by day. They will bring their feeling to a class and this would affect to result of the lesson. Boekaerts (1996) noted down that researchers apply theoretical frameworks and methods for studying emotions in the classroom. At the same time, Schwab (1996) and other researchers found information describe the consequences of emotions that can name as teacher anxiety, stress and bad behaviors in class. Face to face interaction is important in the classroom especially in speaking lessons because emotion between teachers and students builds in this interaction (Feiman-Nemser & Re'millard, 1996). According to Härtel & Page (2009), emotion can affect a person to others. That means teachers' emotion relate to students' emotion in some ways. Bakker (2005) made a survey on flow experiences between students and teachers in music class. He found that three aspects are absorption, enjoyment, enthusiasm in class. In conclusion, he said that students tend to copy emotion from their teacher such as cheerful, joyful, happy,... Therefore, emotion is a good way to transfer work enjoyment. The student will show good speaking performance when they feel happy. On the other hand, poor speaking performance come from students who have bad mood. The teacher should provide a rich environment where are enjoyable, comfortable and free to communicate. learning environment is important to desire students passionate about studying English. If a speaking lesson have real conversation, students will like to practice English and apply it for real situation. Foreigner teacher should join in English speaking class because it's a change for student to practice English and improve speaking skills. Moreover, students can used to speak English with foreigners and boot their confidence.

Psychology is a factor that affects students in speaking lesson. Nunan (1999), Yi Htwe (2011) and Robby (2010) noted down that students are afraid of making mistakes when they speak English in class. Fear of mistake is relevant to correction and negative evaluation (Aftat, 2011). He and Chen (2010) pointed out that students are laughed at by their friends if they speak something wrong in speaking lessons. Therefore, teachers should be careful when they correct students' mistake because they can offend the students. The teacher can also give them speak freely so that they speak naturally without worrying make mistakes. Shyness is a negative emotion that most students face with if they speak in English class. According to Baldwin (2011), the normal reaction of students is shy when the teacher requires them to speak in front of people. They would forget the information about what they want to say. The teacher should encourage students to overcome the fear of shyness and help reduce this feeling. Horwitz (Summer, 1986) demonstrated that anxiety is a feeling of anxiousness and nervousness that affects students' performance. The teacher should create a comfortable and relax atmosphere in speaking lessons. In that way, students don't feel under pressure in English speaking. Some students are lack of confidence when they don't understand conversation during speaking class. Nunan (1999) explained that students have communication apprehension because they think they can't speak English.

Based on the review of other researcher above, this study will follow: teacher's role in speaking lesson, class activities, speaking level and psychology of student. The research hypothesis is set out as follows:

- H1: Teacher's role impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons
- H2: Class activities impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons
- H3: The level of English- speaking impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons
- H4: Psychology of student impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons

3. Methodology

The data collected by 45 English-majored students at HUFU. The quantitative method applied for this study to find impact factors and suggest good solutions. An online questionnaire was to be used in this study. The student answered the questions about factors that motivate them in speaking lessons. They evaluated the impact factors through an interval scale to show their opinion. After that the data analyzed to make the issue clearly. As a result, we can investigate in the discussion sector.

3.1. Research questions

The study was conducted to find answers to the following questions:

1. Does the teacher's role impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons?

2. How do class activities impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons?
3. Does the level of English- speaking impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons?
4. How does the psychology of student impact to the motivation of student in speaking lessons?

3.2. Setting and participants

3.2.2 Research setting

The survey was taken place at HUFU where over 500 students have learned English in the Foreign Languages Department. An online questionnaire was sent to the student through email, Facebook Messenger, Facebook group. After they filled in the questionnaire form, the form was submitted and collected automatically

3.2.2 Research participants

There were 45 students who participated in the survey. They involved in freshman, sophomore and junior. The age of students was in the range of 18 to 22. Both male and female joined in the survey. All of them answered an online questionnaire and gave their own opinions.

3.3. Data collection instruments

The method that was used in the process of the survey was a questionnaire. According to Preston (2009), a questionnaire survey is a technique that gathers necessary information such as attributes, attitudes, or actions of respondents by structured questions. Some advantages of the questionnaire are cheap and easy for the questioners. In this way, researchers can save time to collect the data and make the survey in a wide range. The information can gather without the researcher's presence. Besides, the respondents feel comfortable and take free time to answer the questionnaire survey.

3.4. Research procedure

The research was conducted to these steps:

- The researcher created a questionnaire survey using Google form
- The researcher sent to English- majored students in the question Foreign Languages Department.
- The participants were students who experienced in speaking lesson.
- The result of the questionnaire took 4 days to collect the data.
- The researcher received 45 respondents.

3.4.1. Sample size, power and precision

The participants were chosen randomly in 500 students in the Foreign Languages Department. They used to study Speaking 1, Speaking 2 and Speaking 3 which were subjects for English- majored students. There were 45 respondents accepted. The sample and number of respondents were enough with the expectation. Each respondent showed individual opinion so that the sample was completely honest.

3.4.2. Research design and measures

The descriptive design used in this study. This design relies on a questionnaire to collect data. The questionnaire involved 10 questions that evaluated students about the teacher's role, class activities, the level of English- speaking and the psychology of students in speaking lessons. Each question shows participants' satisfaction with the questions in the survey. The methods reliability of assessors used to enhance the quality of the measurements.

4. Results

The questionnaires were sent to English- major students who have learned English in the Foreign Languages Department. Freshman, sophomore and junior are subject to the survey. Totally the researcher collected 45 respondents. The student's answers showed more clearly by data and charts below.

You are a student
45 câu trả lời

Figure 4.1 Year of students studying in HUPI

The survey conducted in English- majored students who studied in HUPI from one to four years. They experienced in English- speaking lesson so that they can give their opinion honestly.

❖ Questionnaire no.1

1. Your teachers help you so much in speaking lessons (correct grammar, improve pronunciation, give new vocabularies,...)

45 câu trả lời

Figure 4.2 Students' opinion about the teacher's role in speaking lessons

The chart showed students' opinions about the teacher's role in speaking lessons. In general, teachers often helped their students to correct grammar, improve pronunciation and give them new vocabulary, etc. Another opinion stated that the teacher sometimes checked grammar, corrected errors of pronunciation and gave new vocabularies. This meant that teachers played an indispensable role in speaking class because students needed someone to guide and help them improve speaking skills.

2. Your teachers support and encourage you when you make mistakes in speaking.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.2

Figure 4.3 Students' opinion about the feedback of teacher affecting student

The feedback of the teacher was important to students when students made mistakes. Most students agreed that their teacher supported and encouraged them when they made mistakes in speaking. However, there are a few students who strongly disagree with this state. According to the figure, teachers need to give positive feedback in class although students make mistakes. Let students free to talk and express their opinion. Teachers can correct errors later and avoid offending students.

3. Class activities make you excited and want to study in English speaking lessons (E.g: group work, games, role play,...).

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.3

Figure 4.4 Students' opinion about class activities affecting student

Over 60 percent of attendants (30 students) in the survey agreed that class activities make them excited in English speaking lessons. It evidenced that class activities can motivate students in speaking lessons. Teachers should apply for group work, games, role play,... in speaking lessons after that students can have a chance to speak. Besides, students can improve speaking performance through class activities in speaking lessons. However, another student gave a neutral answer. In their opinion, class activities didn't affect them so that it depends on teachers if they want to create class activities.

4. Class activities help you remember vocabularies, support long term memory, speed up memory, retrieve and recall information easily.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.4

Figure 4.5 Students' opinion about class activities helpful to students

There were 62,2 percent of students (28 students) who agreed that class activities helped them remember vocabulary, support long term memory, speed up memory, retrieve and recall information easily. From the chart, teachers can see how important of class activities are. Therefore, teachers should create more activities in class because it is good for students when they join in those activities. However, contrasted ideas pointed out that class activities didn't help much for students in some cases.

5. Your speaking skill is

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.5

Figure 4.6 Students' opinion about their level of English- speaking skill

Figure 4.6 showed the level of English- speaking skills among the surveyed people. Only 11.1 percent (5 students) said that their speaking skill is good. Most students believed that their speaking was not too bad (66,7%). There are 20 percent thought that their speaking skill was bad. Students should divide into a speaking class that is suitable for them. Students tend to feel bored when they cannot follow the flow of the speaking lesson. If teachers know the level of English- speaking skill in students, it is easier for teachers to choose an effective teaching method. Teachers should find out what the weakness of students is after that teachers can help students improve their speaking skills.

❖ Questionnaire no.6

Figure 4.7 Students' opinion about English speaking ability for communication

6. Can you speak any topic in daily life and communicate easily with foreigners?

45 câu trả lời

Only 12 students said that they can speak any topic in daily life and communicate easily with foreigners. Most students answered that they weren't sure they can communicate with foreigners. Look at this result, teachers should teach students about English in communication especially in speaking lessons. Students like to study something that they can use in daily life. Moreover, speaking lessons should be practical lessons. The lessons' content needs to be close to reality and can be applied to future jobs. If the lessons' content is attractive students, they will want to study and join the class excitedly.

7. You are afraid of making mistakes when you speak English.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.7

Figure 4.8 Students' opinion about the fear of making mistakes

55.6 percent – 25 students agreed that they were afraid of making mistakes in speaking English. This fear prevents students from speaking performance. They are scared because the teacher can criticize them and their friends laugh at them. However, the other 13.3 percent (6 students) disagreed with the state. They thought that it was fine to make mistakes because other students were the same as them. Teachers should create a supportive atmosphere to reduce students' nervousness. In

addition, the teacher avoids negative evaluations that make them offend. Teachers need to explain to students that making mistakes is completely normal. That mistakes are worth to discuss and helpful for experience later.

8. You are very shy when you speak English in front of people.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.8

Figure 4.9 Students' opinion about shyness in speaking English

The majority thought that shyness didn't affect their speaking performance. However, there were 19 students said that they were very shy when they spoke English in front of people. Felling of shyness occurs because they are lack of confidence and anxious about making mistakes. This leads to students being silent in the classroom even though it is a speaking lesson. Teachers need to observe and know individual who is shy in speaking English. Those students need to be encouraged and care especially. Let students practice speaking English as soon as possible to help them get used to speaking English.

9. You are anxious when you speak English.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.9

Figure 4.10 Students' opinion about anxiousness in speaking English

The survey showed that half of the people in the survey felt anxious about speaking English. They worry about their ability to speak English, grammar and vocabulary poorly. From this figure, teachers should create more oral activities to reduce anxiousness and motivate students in speaking lessons. In addition, teachers can provide positive reinforcement and build an eased environment in class to support students' confidence. Teachers should accept the answers of students in a variety of cased. The opposite opinions were 20 percent (9 students). For them, anxiety is not an obstacle for them during speaking lessons.

10. You are lack of confidence when you speak English.

45 câu trả lời

❖ Questionnaire no.10

Figure 4.11 Students' opinion about confidence in speaking English

The majority of students said that they were lack of confidence in speaking English. 9 students disagreed with this opinion. Most students are not confident because of their low English- speaking ability. To help students build confidence, teachers should provide more oppportunities for students to practice pronunciation, stress and intonation in speaking lessons. Furthermore, speaking lessons should be a comfortable atmosphere to converse freely. Teachers need to encourage students to use English in conversations and compliment them.

5. Discussion

The survey showed a new perspective on the factors that motivate English- majored students in speaking lessons. The hypotheses were verified by the student in the Foreign Languages Department. After considering, some advice was suggested.

The research questions were clarified by English- major students. There are initial successes thanks to the contribution of the students. The researcher was received positive feedback from participants. English- major students expressed their opinion about the teacher's role in speaking lessons. Most of them gave positive opinions but they also suggested ideas for teachers to teach English speaking lessons. In addition,

teachers can understand the expectation of the student in class activities to meet students' needs. Class activities are beneficial for students to remember vocabulary, support long term memory, speed up memory, retrieve and recall information easily. The student said that the interaction between teachers and students through speaking lessons is carried out easily and makes the classroom more successful. The level of English- speaking was discussed in the survey question. The student assessed their English- speaking ability and gave opinion honestly. Student opinions are a source of reference for teachers after that they can design an appropriate curriculum for their students. Last but not least, teachers can know clearly about students' psychology. Look at students' evaluation in the final questions of the survey, teachers can understand students' psychology in speaking lessons. Students have to face with many problems of psychology in English speaking. They are fear of making mistakes, shyness, anxiousness and lack of confidence. Seeing students' weakness in speaking performance, teachers can help students overcome psychological problems.

The study pointed out some feature of speaking lessons that is helpful for teachers and students. Look at the survey, teachers understand more about their students and give suitable teaching methods. Moreover, students gave feedback about speaking lessons honestly to evaluate the quality of lessons. The results of the study are not only meaningful to the speaking classes but also contribute to the Foreign of Language Department in teaching methods later. The opinions expressed in this study may be useful to readers but there are still limitations that need to be improved.

6. Conclusions

The aim of the study found factors that motivate English- major students at HUFU in speaking lessons. There were four hypotheses in this study. They included the teacher's role, class activities, the level of English- speaking and the psychology of students. English- major students discussed the hypotheses in the survey. The survey used a questionnaire that included ten questions to conduct on 45 students. The finding of the study found that internal and external factors that need to be combined to make speaking lessons successful. They might come from the teacher but students also make a significant contribution to the speaking class. Speaking lessons really attracted students when they met their students' interests. The study paper pointed out the disadvantages of English- speaking lessons that need to be improved. Students and teachers should consult the study to find some solutions for the method of learning and teaching English speaking.

Some limitations of the study cannot be avoidable. The number of students participating in the study was not much so that it didn't give an overview of the research. Some students didn't assess the questions in accordance with their own factors. The time for doing research was quite short so the research is not detailed.

The researcher hoped that the limitation in the study could become experiences for the other researchers in their further studies. There are other factors to motivate

students in speaking lessons so that the other researcher can make a study of this wide area.

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